
Navigating New Narratives: The Bodo Tribes Storytelling through Social Media Platforms

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ABSTRACT

This study examines how the Bodo community of Assam is reimagining its cultural heritage on social media narratives. Previously marginalized in larger narratives, the Bodos now use online platforms to tell their history, folklore, and contemporary lives. The project aims to explore the role of social media in the preservation and re-creation of Bodo heritage, in terms of influencing community engagement and external perceptions. Utilizing qualitative research, the study employs content analysis of Bodo-centric social media accounts and an analysis of internet storytelling trends. Findings reveal that social media is a critical tool for cultural preservation that provides opportunity for intergenerational knowledge sharing in addition to addressing socio-political concerns. However, the internet divide and misinformation on the internet pose a significant challenge. The study ascertains that social media is not only a medium of storytelling but also a powerful means of building Bodo identity and community solidarity in today's age.

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Introduction

Tribes have been deeply embedded in the life of India, contributing to its rich heritage and multicultural society. The term "tribe" comes from the Latin term "tribus," which originally referred to the different parts of the Roman state. The term "tribe" has been explained by the Cambridge Dictionary as a group of people with a common language, culture, and history and who traditionally inhabit the countryside or hills. Tribal populations in India constitute approximately 8.6% of the population, as per the Census of 2011, and have traditionally been referred to as Adivasis, a name that recognizes them as the aboriginal people of the country. They have, over time, been legally established as Scheduled Tribes in an effort to care for their socio-economic and political interests.

The geography profoundly affects the diversity of tribal communities, which in turn determines their cultural traditions, lifestyle, and economic pursuits. Tribes living in mountainous terrain have certain differences from those living in coastal or desert tracts. Their conventional means of earning a living—like hunting, gathering, and cultivation—emphasize a close relationship with nature. Such sustainable modes of living have much to teach us about hardiness and versatility.

The Bodo people, one of the oldest and largest indigenous groups of Northeast India, predominantly dwell in the verdant Brahmaputra Valley of Assam. Being descended from the Indo-Mongoloid stock and belonging to the Tibeto-Burman language family, the Bodos have been known as "Kirata" in ancient Indian literature. Down the ages, in spite of contact with other ethnic groups, the Bodos have preserved their distinct identity. Assertively, they call themselves "Boro" or "Bodosa," which signifies "sons of Bodo." Bodo language, as recognized under the Indian Constitution, has been modernized by adopting the Devanagari script, an achievement made easier by the initiatives of the Bodo Sahitya Sabha. (Tripathy S., 2019)

Bodos mainly live in the Bodoland Territorial Region (BTR) of Assam, including the districts of Kokrajhar, Chirang, Baksa, and Udalguri. They live in small numbers in West Bengal, Arunachal Pradesh, Nagaland, Nepal, and Bangladesh. The community is organized into groups like Swargiary, Basumatary, Narzary, Khakhlory, and Borgoyary, which form the basis of social cohesion. Their houses were in the past separated from other non-Bodo societies, but contemporary developments have enhanced interaction.

The Bodos follow Bathouism, a cult of nature that venerates five fundamental elements—earth, water, air, fire, and sky—represented by the holy Sijou plant. Their rich cultural life includes unique music, dance, fairs, dressing, and ornamentation. Socio-political concerns have, over a period of time, led to demands for autonomy, which finally resulted in the formation of the Bodoland Territorial Council (BTC) in Assam. (Tripathy S. , Ecosystem Study of the Dalbari, Daklabari, Dakshinsuppa and Golibari Villages, 2019)

Media is a powerful factor in determining the texture of society. It exists in various forms—TV, radio, newspaper, and the internet—and is an effective means of conveying information, instruction, and entertainment. Mass media, as considered by Biagi (2015), include television, newspaper, radio, magazines, books, recordings, and films, with the internet being the last of them. Media's impacts are widespread in nature, on public sentiment, cultural behavior, and socio-political discourse process. In India, it was used to instill self-reliance, education, and democracy, having been termed famously by Jawaharlal Nehru as the "watchdog of democracy."

The fast pace of media expansion, especially post-liberalization in the 1990s, has changed the access to information. The development of digital technology and satellite television has brought access to knowledge and opportunities to marginalized communities. Researchers such as Ekoja (2003) observe how mass media have made information easy to disseminate and enhanced levels of education. Media accessibility, however, is dependent on literacy, economic factors, and geography. Tribal groups, who live mostly in rural areas, are cut off from media access due to social and economic disparities.

Right from the start, traditional folk media has been the primary means of communication between tribes. But with the advent of government initiatives and sophisticated media technologies, outreach has increased significantly. The entry of Direct-to-Home (DTH) services has indeed overcome the distances and costs, enabling tribal communities to access crucial education and welfare-related information.

This study explores the contribution of social media towards the conservation and adaptation of Bodo cultural practices. With their wide coverage, social media websites have become indispensable for the promotion of heritage. The study examines how these websites conserve traditional customs and render them adaptable to the modern context. The study examines the contribution of social media to the construction and negotiation of Bodo identity, allowing the group to express its culture and deepen its sense of belonging.

The research also investigates the problems of digitalization, such as cultural misrepresentation, dilution, and digital literacy gaps between generations. Although some see social media as a means of maintaining culture, others see it as a threat to traditional ways of life. The way people view these elements provides a deeper analysis of its impact on the Bodo people's cultural identity.

Employing a mix of primary and secondary research methodologies, the research targets Instagram and YouTube as the primary sources of data. These two data sources are rich in visual and textual content, graphically showcasing Bodo tradition in reels, stories, and videos. Netnography, an ethnography that is specially tailored for online groups, is employed by the research to research digital interaction. This covert form of participant observation documents real interaction, offering insightful data on how Bodo people utilize social media to represent culture.

The gathered material is examined thematically to reveal patterns in cultural preservation, adaptation, and online engagement. Ancillary data, such as books, journal articles, and research papers, offer context, allowing for the placement of conclusions within wider debates around Bodo culture and digitalization.

A qualitative research methodology permits a deep examination of these dynamics, with a strong focus on the cultural and emotional aspects involved. Nevertheless, the research acknowledges some limitations, such as the digital divide among the Bodo community, which might exclude those without internet access. Social media postings often reflect idealized portrayals of cultural practices, which might differ from the realities encountered offline. Additionally, although Netnography is effective in the study of online behavior, it is inadequate in studying offline cultural practices, creating a gap in understanding the totality of their socio-cultural environment.

Notwithstanding these issues, this study makes important contributions to understanding how social media help to bring about cultural change and preservation among the Bodo people. In examining online narratives, the study identifies the changing nature of Bodo identity and tradition in contemporary times.

Review of Literature

The research paper by Nayanjyoti Gogoi, "*Bodo Movement in Assam: Causes of its Origin and Its Impacts*" (2020), examines the factors leading to the Bodo Movement, such as economic deprivation, cultural marginalization, and political exclusion. It highlights the movement's influence on Assam's socio-political and economic landscape, emphasizing identity politics and the demand for autonomy. The study

concludes that while the movement partially safeguarded Bodo identity, it had limited success in ensuring broader community development.

"An Introductory Study of Bodo Culture, Religion, and Its Relationship with Hinduism" (2017) by Alok Jwhlaw Daimary and Arjundeb Sensarma explores the Bodo people's cultural and religious heritage, focusing on Bathouism's five-fold philosophy and its links to Hinduism, particularly Lord Shiva. The study also examines the impact of external religions like Christianity and Islam and highlights women's roles in preserving Bodo traditions.

Dr. Phanindra Kalita's *"Early History of the Bodos: A Root Cause of Bodo Struggle for Ethnic Identity Formation"* (2019) delves into the historical roots of the Bodo people, emphasizing their migration, settlement, and political evolution. It explores how colonial and postcolonial policies fueled their demand for autonomy, leading to the creation of the Bodoland Territorial Council (BTC). Similarly, his *"Political Demands and Memorandums of the Bodos and the Emergence of Political Consciousness"* (2018) examines the political awakening of the Bodo community, analyzing memoranda submitted to colonial and post-independence governments. The paper highlights how these demands shaped the movement for self-determination, culminating in BTC's establishment.

In *"Bodo Ethnic Assertion and Their Socio-Cultural and Political Awakening"* (2019), Dr. Kalita investigates the impact of the Brahma movement, Christian missionary activities, the Simon Commission, and the Tribal League on Bodo identity formation. The study illustrates how these elements fostered socio-political awareness, ultimately shaping later autonomy movements.

Saswatik Tripathy's *"A Study on the Different Dimensions of the Bodo Tribal Community of Dalbari Village"* (2020) provides an ethnographic study of the Bodos in Baksa district, Assam. It examines their social, cultural, economic, and political structures, highlighting sustainable practices, gender equality, and the significance of traditional religion. The study employs participatory research methods to offer a comprehensive understanding of Bodo tribal life.

Manish Mishra's *"Tribal Development in India: A Sociological Analysis"* (2015) critiques existing tribal development policies, arguing that they often fail due to a one-size-fits-all approach. The study calls for tailored strategies, culturally relevant education, and a redefinition of development goals that respect tribal autonomy. Similarly, *"Scheduled Tribes and the Politics of Inclusion in India"* by Jagannath Ambagudia

explores the state's role in defining tribal status, highlighting how policies of inclusion often lead to further marginalization instead of genuine empowerment.

"Social Media Influencers and the Ethnic World: A Sociological Insight from the Indian Tribes" (2024) by Neelu Rawat, Sunil K. Yadav, and Nidhi Dinker examines how social media platforms influence tribal representation. The study discusses how influencers amplify tribal voices but also risk cultural oversimplification. Using Baudrillard's hyperreality theory, it assesses the balance between authentic portrayal and curated digital identities, emphasizing the transformative potential of social media for cultural preservation.

"Social Media in Changing the Culture of Tribal Community in West Bengal" (2021) by Deblina Talukdar & Jayanta Mete examines how social media influences the cultural patterns of tribal communities in West Bengal across four districts. Using a survey of 500 respondents, it highlights shifts in language use, festivals, food habits, and occupations due to digital engagement. Findings indicate that 68.6% of respondents use non-native languages online, and 89% celebrate festivals beyond traditional ones. Occupational changes were also noted, with many shifting to modern employment due to job opportunities found on social media. The study concludes that while social media fosters cultural transformation, it also raises concerns about identity retention.

"Role of Traditional Folk and Modern Media in Development Communication Among Paniya Tribes in the Nilgiris District" (2022) by Monisha M. & Dr. P.E. Thomas contrasts traditional folk media with modern digital media in shaping the socio-economic lives of the Paniya tribe. Traditional communication methods such as folk songs and rituals remain significant for knowledge transmission, particularly in areas with low literacy. However, modern media like television, mobile phones, and social platforms provide wider educational access. The study highlights challenges such as digital illiteracy and economic barriers that hinder full media utilization. While modern media offers broader exposure, the loss of cultural identity is a growing concern among the Paniya community.

"Awareness of social media as a Promotional Medium for Kulintangan Traditional Music of Sungai Tribes at Paitan" (2021) explores how the Sungai community in Paitan, Sabah, uses social media to promote their traditional Kulintangan music. Surveying 377 respondents, it reveals moderate awareness of social media's potential for cultural promotion. While platforms like WhatsApp, Facebook, and YouTube are popular, their use for sharing cultural music remains low. The study suggests increased

digital literacy programs and initiatives from local organizations to encourage cultural preservation through online platforms.

“Acculturation and Transition in Religious Beliefs and Practices of the Bodos” (2017) by Dinanath Basumatary & Alaka Basumatary investigates the transformation of the Bodo tribe’s religious beliefs due to external influences like Hinduism and Christianity. Traditionally following Bathouism, many Bodos have shifted to structured religious frameworks, leading to modifications in cultural practices. The study emphasizes the need for institutional support to preserve Bathouism while addressing modern challenges.

“Religion and its Reflection on the Culture of the Bodos of Assam” (2019) by Satyendra Kumar Sarmah examines the relationship between religion and Bodo culture, this study highlights Bathou Dharma’s role in shaping societal norms. With modern influences impacting traditional practices, revival movements among the educated Bodo class aim to restore indigenous customs. The study underscores religion as a dynamic force that continues to evolve with external interactions.

Media as Social Change Agent: An Evaluative Study of the Nyishi Tribe of Arunachal Pradesh (2022) This paper by Gyamar Nemeyassesses media’s role in transforming the Nyishi tribe’s socio-political and economic aspects. It highlights media’s power as both an enabler of progress and a potential disruptor of cultural traditions. The study emphasizes the need for balanced media consumption to ensure positive societal changes while preserving heritage.

A Study of Mass Media Impact on the Gujjar Tribe of Chamba and Kangra Districts of Himachal Pradesh” (2019) this research by Suresh Kumar explores mass media’s impact on education, cultural awareness, and political participation among the Gujjar tribe. While media enhances access to government programs, challenges like illiteracy and economic barriers limit its reach. The study recommends community radio and better connectivity for effective tribal empowerment.

Research Methodology

The current study employs a combination of qualitative research approaches to examine how social media builds and sustains the cultural practices of the Bodo people. The employment of primary as well as secondary sources of information, the research seeks to ensure enhanced comprehension of cultural expression in the online platform.

i. Data Collection

The study focused on Instagram and YouTube as the major sources of information. The two platforms were selected because they have an enormous repository of user-generated content that visually and narratively captures Bodo cultural identity. Instagram offers a collection of pictures, reels, and stories of traditional attire, rituals, and festivals, and YouTube offers long videos and lectures about Bodo culture. The two platforms offer avenues for exploring how the Bodo people utilize digital platforms to preserve their culture in depth.

ii. Netnography

To analyse social media posts, the study employs Netnography, a qualitative method adapted from ethnography to the online environment. It involves covert participant observation, whereby the researcher witnesses online interaction in their normal environment without disclosing their research agenda. Through online post, comment, and interaction pattern monitoring, the study records how Bodo people and groups present their culture online.

iii. Content Analysis

After data is gathered on YouTube and Instagram, it is subject to a thorough content analysis. Messages, videos, comments are analyzed systematically in an attempt to find recurring patterns and themes. Of interest are how traditional customs are represented, how the stories of Bodo identity shift online, and how the younger generations interact with cultural heritage using social media. It is through such analysis that the manner in which traditional customs evolve in the digital age can be comprehended.

iv. Secondary Data Sources

Secondary data are gathered, as a complement to primary research, from scholarly articles, journals, and texts. This establishes historical and theoretical contexts, which facilitate integrated comprehension of the findings. By situating social media discourse in historical and academic contexts, the research bridges the gap between digital and analogue sources of cultural heritage.

Theoretical Framework

This study utilizes Denis McQuail's Theory of Media and Society, 2010, to examine the impact of social media on the cultural representation of the Bodo tribe. McQuail points out the interdependence of society and media, noting that media not only creates but is created by social structures, values, and cultural

norms. His theory examines central themes of power and inequality, social integration, and the role of the media in social change.

Social media is now an important medium for the Bodo community to carry and share their cultural identity. Previously relying on word-of-mouth oral traditions, the Bodo community now uses electronic media like YouTube and Instagram to share their folklore, songs, and traditional practices with the global community. This change brings a sense of immense pride and belongingness, particularly among the youth.

Secondly, McQuail's theory also identifies the position of media in power relations. Social media enables the Bodo people to own their own story, counter mainstream misrepresentation, and campaign for cultural and political causes. It also provides economic opportunities through web marketing of traditional arts and performances.

Applying McQuail's model, this study investigates how online platforms function not only as means for the preservation of culture but also as drivers for social change among the Bodo tribe.

This research uses Stuart Hall's Cultural Studies Theory to examine how social media enables the Bodo tribe to reclaim their cultural identity and resist dominant representations. Hall's theory positions media's role in the construction of dominant ideologies, as well as media as a site of resistance. His encoding/decoding model explains the processes of how media messages are created and consumed, allowing marginalized groups to negotiate or subvert dominant narratives.

Previously, the Bodo have been less represented in India's mass media. However, on social media sites like YouTube and Instagram, there is a site of cultural assertion. Through the production of their own media—documenting their traditional festivals, music, and language—the Bodo challenge selective representation and defend their culture. This aligns with Hall's idea of negotiating and subverting dominant ideologies through alternative media.

Dominant media encode hegemonic messages, disempowering indigenous voices. Bodos, however, decode and recontextualize such messages using social media, claiming their cultural visibility. Young Bodos also act as mediators between tradition and modern times, combining traditional ideas with modern practices. Hall's theory offers the critical lens through which the process of how the digital space assists the Bodo tribe in moving from passive recipients of media to active agents of culture-making can be explained.

Findings and Data Analysis

This study examines engagement metrics from four Instagram accounts—Soharu, Souls of Green, Onladao and The Bodoland Things focusing on how the Bodo community uses social media to showcase its cultural identity. Key themes include food, festivals, rural life, and cultural events, revealing patterns in audience interaction and challenges in digital representation.

1. Engagement Trends Across Instagram Accounts

a. Likes and Shares as Indicators of Popularity

Soharu shows the highest engagement, with posts exceeding 32.7k likes and 2,439 shares, particularly those featuring traditional food like silkworm dishes and duck with white gourd. This highlights food's significance as a cultural marker. Souls of Green and Onladao receive moderate engagement (99–989 likes per post), with food vlogs and festival content performing best. The Bodoland Things gains traction through influencer collaborations, with some posts reaching 7,892 likes and 578 shares.

b. Comments and Audience Interaction

Comments reflect a highly engaged audience appreciative of cultural content. Posts featuring food, festivals, and traditions receive positive reactions, though unconventional food choices (e.g., silkworms) elicit mixed responses. Festival-related content, like Bodo Mahotsav and Bihu, receives enthusiastic engagement, suggesting that audiences, especially non-Bodos, are drawn to cultural celebrations.

2. Popular Themes and Their Impact

a. Food as a Cultural Symbol

Food content consistently attracts the highest engagement. Dishes like roselle leaves with pork and Bodo thali receive thousands of likes, demonstrating food's role in cultural representation. Cooking vlogs combining storytelling and personal narratives generate more interaction than static food photography.

b. Cultural Festivals and Community Events

Posts covering Bodo Mahotsav, Bihu, and Bodo Sahitya Sabha gain significant traction, reinforcing festivals as cultural touchpoints. Collaborations with influencers, such as those seen in The Bodoland Things, boost engagement, highlighting the importance of strategic partnerships in digital storytelling.

c. Representation of Rural and Village Life

Village vlogs provide an authentic glimpse into Bodo life but receive lower engagement than food or festival posts. This suggests audiences prefer content with strong cultural storytelling elements over general depictions of rural settings.

3. Audience Behavior and Interpretation

a. Appreciation for Cultural Representation

Many comments reflect nostalgia, pride, and curiosity, with users seeking more information on Bodo traditions. This indicates that social media effectively bridges generational and geographical gaps.

b. The Role of Influencer Collaborations

Collaborations with well-known Bodo personalities significantly enhance engagement, expanding audience reach and reinforcing cultural narratives.

c. Cultural Sensitivities and Mixed Reactions

While most responses are positive, indigenous food traditions sometimes face scrutiny from external audiences. Content creators must navigate these differences by educating viewers on cultural significance.

YouTube has turned out to be a significant platform for the Bodo tribe to display their traditions, daily life, and rich cultural heritage to the world. Observations of three YouTube channels—Helina Daimary, Sunita Boro, and Janas Vlog—reflect how social media is being used as a platform to record and preserve Bodo traditions and engage actively with the viewers. These uploaders feature diverse topics related to Bodo culture, e.g., lifestyle vlogs, cooking preparations, and cultural practices, and thereby make their content informative and engaging.

Janas Vlog presents another window into the life of the students who study in a Bodo medium school. Through frequent updates, the vlogger is reporting on the everyday life of the students as well as the colorful activities of the school. Throughout the data collection process, the vlogger captured the school annual festival, revealing the sincerity, passion, and rigorous efforts of the students in hosting and participating in the event. This content not only reflects the academic environment of the Bodo schools but also showcases the cultural heritage and social morals that define the Bodo way of life. Through these

experiences, Janas Vlog is contributing significantly towards the preservation and promotion of the tribe's academic and social culture.

Helina Daimary's content reflects the rural Bodo way of life, and she has received a lot of traction from her community. Some Bodo viewers appreciate her effort at representing their traditional way of life in an authentic way, as evidenced in the positive feedback accompanying her videos. However, some viewers have criticized her content choice. While many appreciate her authenticity, others criticize her for occasionally straying into mainstream social media content, such as popular 'Get Ready With Me' (GRWM) videos, rather than staying centered on representing Bodo culture. In addition, some viewers have critiqued her traditional clothes, particularly identifying the proper way to wear the 'dokhona' and the omission of 'aronai' in some videos. One controversy that arose was over her decision to wear traditional clothes when working in paddy fields, with critics accusing her of making the decision based more on content needs than functionality. This shows how cultural representation sometimes raises controversy around authenticity and expectations that come with it in indigenous communities.

Sunita Boro, however, gets an abundance of positive feedback for her vlogs, which delve into the reality of village life and the art of traditional food preparation. She posts regularly about her harvest, showcasing with pride the diversity of plants and vegetables she cultivates in her garden. In addition, her cooking vlogs invite viewers to explore a rich fabric of Bodo traditional food, offering a window into the world of Bodo cuisine. In one of the most popular videos, she showed the ancient art of catching fish with her own hands from a muddy pond, leaving her viewers spellbound. A deluge of comments flowed in, appreciating her content, as viewers celebrated the authenticity of her videos and were awed by the delectable dishes she prepares.

These YouTube vlogs serve as online archives, documenting and showcasing Bodo culture in great detail while seamlessly bridging the gap between traditional ways of life and the contemporary world. They give the Bodo tribe a platform to present their rich heritage to a global audience while meaningfully engaging with their own people. In the colourful space of social media, the Bodo people can celebrate their cultural identity, adeptly navigating the changing expectations and interpretations of their beloved traditions.

Discussion

Social media has equally been an instrumental vehicle for the Bodo community to maintain and promote their identity. The historical background of the Bodo people is one in which their social-political pursuits were highly influenced by their culture and language. Although oral narrative and community activities have helped preserve the culture in the past among the Bodos, digital means, particularly Instagram, have eased their way into reaching out with their identity to more people. Instagram audience analytics on Soharu, Souls of Green, Onladao, and The Bodoland Things reveal how well stories are communicated through image storytelling, particularly of food and festivals.

Religion, specifically Bathouism, is an important aspect of Bodo culture. Social media helps to show and share religious practice. People often share rituals, ancestor worship, and traditional festivals like Bwisagu. This helps the youth and others to recognize and appreciate Bodo spiritual practices. However, the mixing of Bathouism, Hinduism, and Christianity shows that Bodo identity is always changing while staying grounded.

The wider context of media impact on societies is how social media has revolutionized representation of indigenous peoples. Before, marginalized groups could not be seen in mainstream media, but platforms such as Instagram give them the space to narrate their own stories and enable the Bodo tribe to be masters of their own narrative. While popular topics are food, festivals, and rural lives, the different reactions to indigenous food practices show cultural differences in perception. Despite these, the Bodo tribe successfully leverages digital spaces for community formation, advocacy, and cultural preservation. Social media is therefore record and connection and promotes increased awareness of Bodo heritage in a more digital world.

Limitations

While this method is informative, there are some limitations that must be taken into account. The study focuses on Instagram and YouTube alone, excluding other social media platforms and offline culture. Not all members of the Bodo community are on these platforms, and therefore gaps in representation can arise. Social media is sometimes staged, edited, and manipulated by algorithms on the platforms, which may not reflect actual cultural practices. Netnography, while effective in digital ethnographic studies, does not account for offline cultural processes, which limits the study's ability to compare online and offline expressions. Content analysis also has a subjective component to it, as interpretations can be influenced by the opinion and cultural experience of the researcher.

Conclusion

The study brings into view how the Assam Bodo people are using social media as a medium for documenting and sharing their cultural histories, in effect bridging the gap between the traditional and the modern influences. The digital media have enabled the individuals to share their accounts, market their heritage, and access a wider audience. However, issues of limited digital access, cases of misrepresentation, and external political pressures still impede their online presence. Although social media offers a medium for self-presentation, its efficacy depends on access to the internet, government censorship, and social acceptance. The study calls for greater digital inclusion, positive policy environments, and media literacy programs to enable the Bodo people to express their cultural identity in the face of digital challenges. Finally, the study confirms that narrative self-presentation on social media is a powerful instrument for marginalized societies to project their voice and make their customs relevant in an ever-evolving environment.

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